

Innovative concepts and technologies for ECologically sustainable NUTRIent management in agriculture aiming to prevent, mitigate and eliminate pollution in soils, water, and air

Newsletter – Issue 2

April 2024

WELCOME

Welcome to the second edition of the Econutri Newsletter! Within these pages, you will find news and updates on our activities. We invite you to subscribe and explore our website! Follow us on social media and learn more about the world of Econutri.

[Econutri website](#)

Bridging Continents

Econutri Chinese collaboration takes roots!

The Chinese segment of **Econutri** is officially underway! On November 17, 2023, the kick-off meeting for the Chinese part of the EU-China cooperation project **Econutri** took place. With the EU segment having commenced a year ago (29 November 2022), **Econutri** is now operating at full capacity. The meeting was held at the [China Agricultural University](#) (CAU) in Beijing. The overall goal is to minimize nutrient losses (NO₃-N and P) to water bodies and the atmosphere resulting from agricultural activities in both animal and plant production, which are crucial topics for both China and European countries. This event marks a **significant milestone** for **Econutri**, highlighting the collaboration between Chinese partners and the rest of the consortium. More information [here](#).

Project Framework

This project has received funding from the European Union Horizon Europe Innovation program under the Grant Agreement No. 101081858.

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Celebrating the first year of Econutri

General Assembly in Turin Italy 22–24 November 2023

All partners celebrated the first year of **Econutri** in Turin, Italy. The [Università degli Studi di Torino](#) (UNITO), our host, orchestrated an outstanding meeting with 90 in-person participants and a few joining online, held at the premises of Circolo del Design.

Econutri was honored to host the External Advisory Board, whose valuable feedback has further strengthened our efficiency in pursuing project objectives. Additionally, we were delighted to welcome representatives from five of our stakeholders, out of a total of 47, who had the opportunity to introduce their organizations and express their keen interest in the processes and outcomes of the **Econutri** project. More details on our [website](#).

Main accomplishments

During the last six months all partners have been working towards **Econutri's** main goals and several highlights are described below.

The initial trials compared various cultivation techniques, focusing on nutrient management to enhance yield and quality while reducing losses. Winter intercropping trials faced challenges like frost intolerance, leading to adaptations. Ongoing analysis of crop nutritional content continues amidst erratic weather conditions.

Experimental testing and validation of soil monitoring systems are ongoing, along with calibration experiments for different types of sensors. Implementation of fertilizer management based on digital decision support systems and crop-specific plans is underway across multiple farms, aiming to enhance sustainability in agriculture. Practical abstract submissions and farmer engagement efforts have also progressed, though it is an ongoing process, signifying increasing support and participation from stakeholders. Additionally, the methodology to conduct a life cycle assessment is being finalized in order to evaluate selected innovations' environmental impacts.

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The AUA Team launches a spinoff company to exploit an innovative technology of Econutri

In early January, a spinoff company was founded by the Agricultural University of Athens (AUA) team of **Econutri**, named “NUTRISENSE – Nature-based Solutions for Nutrient Management in Agriculture P.C.”, shortly referenced as “[NUTRISENSE PC](#)”. The main goal is to support growers in applying economically viable and environment-friendly fertilization practices in horticultural crops. To achieve this goal, the company deploys a novel decision support system termed NutriSense which includes two versions, one for soil-grown crops (SOIL NutriSense) and a second one for soilless crops (SOILLESS NutriSense). Read more [here](#).

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NUTRISENSE PC participated as an exhibitor with its own stand at the agricultural exhibition [AGROTICA2024](#) 1-4 February, 2024, in Thessaloniki disseminating the innovations elaborated in **Econutri** project.

NUTRISENSE PC was also presented by the AUA team in the 3rd International Workshop on Vertical Farming ([VertiFarm2024](#)) on Jan. 18 2024. More details [here](#).

Optimization of nutrient supply in leafy vegetables grown in vertical farming using the Decision Support System NUTRISENSE

Dimitrios Savvas, Evangelos Giannothanasis, Lena Voulgari, Georgia Ntatsi

Agricultural University of Athens, Laboratory of Vegetable Production, Iera Odos 75, 11855 Athens, Greece

MANAGEMENT OF NUTRITION IN VERTICAL FARMING

Vertical farming takes place in soilless cropping systems with nutrient solution recirculation, where there is limited buffering capacity for the nutrient status in the root zone.

Thus, to maintain an optimal nutrient status in the root environment, vertical farmers frequently flush out the recirculating nutrient solution and replace it with a new one.

However, the discharge of nutrient solution weakens the environmental sustainability of this cropping system.

Econutri in the spotlight

1. Our partner [Universita Degli Studi di Torino](#) (UNITO), and stakeholder [BIOGAS WIPPTAL](#), showcased the Econutri project at [Ecomondo - The Green Technology Expo](#) in Rimini, Italy on 7-10 November, 2023. This international event hosts the leading companies in environmental technologies, which present their work and share ideas about circular economy and green innovations to promote the ecological transition. More details [here](#).

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2. Our partner [INHORT](#), hosted on December 6 2023, in Skierniewice, Poland a training session titled “MICROBIOLOGICAL FERTILIZER PRODUCTS effective in improving crop quality and soil fertility”. More details [here](#).

3. Our partner [Leibniz Institute of Vegetable and Ornamental Crops \(IGZ\)](#) showcased on 23-26 January, 2024 at the [IPM2024](#) in Essen, Germany [International Trade Fair for Plants](#), the Cascade Hydroponics innovation (by UTH) as a small model representation of the Econutri project. The QR code depicted in the picture is linked to the [IGZ](#) website, where the Econutri webpage appears by clicking the main images. Read more [here](#).

Exciting Field Innovations unfolding since February 2024

[University of Thessaly](#) is working on soilless cultivation to conserve water and reduce fertilizer use, testing a cascade hydroponic system for cherry tomatoes.

[Augmenta](#) Agronomy Team advances sustainable agriculture, conducting nitrogen applications and on-site assessments crucial for the right pilot design, across 30 hectares in Thessaly region, Greece, in collaboration with the Agricultural University of Athens.

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Reinforcing the EU-China Agricultural Partnership

During two significant trips to China, one on 12-15 November 2023, and another from 5-19 April 2024, Rodney Thompson from the [University of Almeria](#) (UAL, ES) and Wim Voogt from [Wageningen University & Research](#) (WUR, NL) reinforced the strong collaboration between European and Chinese partners within the [Econutri](#) project. They provided guidance, exchanged knowledge, and discussed progress with significant Chinese partners and stakeholders across different regions of China, emphasizing sustainable fertigation management in vegetable cropping systems. These visits underscored the shared commitment to improving nutrient use efficiency and reducing NO₃ leaching, showcasing the fruitful EU-China agricultural partnership. More details for [2023 visit](#) and for [April 2024](#).

Future Events

- [Seminar](#): The transition from the ending project Mafigold (NIBIO in Norway) to the new project Econutri, 7 May 2024
- Scientific [workshop](#) "Microbiological preparations in agriculture and environmental protection" Puławy, Poland May 10, 2024.
- [AgritechDay2024](#) 18 June 2024, Belgium
- [8th National Microbiological Symposium](#) "METAGENOMES OF DIFFERENT ENVIRONMENTS" Lublin, Poland, 17-18 June 2024
- 20-year anniversary workshop for NIBIO-China collaborations 18-19 June 2024
- [Agricultural Engineering International Conference](#), AgEng2024 1-4 July 2024
- [Unight](#) - the European Researchers' Night event at Turin University, 29-30 September 2024
- [ISHS International Symposium, titled "1 International Symposium on Protected Cultivation, Nettings and Screens for Mild Climates](#) 23-26 September 2024
- Stakeholder Conference co-organised by the research projects ECONUTRI, TRANS4NUM and PESTNU, 27 September 2024

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